

Molecular dynamics study of adsorption and wetting of mixtures of simple fluids on planar walls

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(Dated: 6 March 2024)

The influence of molecular interactions on adsorption and wetting of binary mixtures was studied by molecular dynamics simulations of sessile droplets on planar walls. The results provide insights into the competing effects between the fluid-fluid interactions and the solid-fluid interactions on adsorption and wetting of mixtures. All interactions were modeled by the Lennard-Jones truncated and shifted (LJTS) potential. The influence of the different dispersive interactions in the fluid mixture as well as those between the fluid components and the wall on the gas and liquid adsorption, the three-phase contact and the contact angle were determined. For the fluid mixtures studied in the present work, the phase behavior and the vapor-liquid interfacial properties are known from recent studies. Together with the present results, this provides a comprehensive picture of the influence of different molecular interactions on the closely related phenomena wetting and adsorption in mixtures.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Wetting and adsorption are closely related phenomena and play an important role in many technical and natural processes. The wetting of a droplet on a planar wall is usually quantified by the contact angle and depends on the properties of all three participating interfaces (solid-liquid, solid-vapor, and vapor-liquid). The adsorption is often quantified by the surface excess, or, with higher resolution, by density profiles. In mixtures, the different components have in general a different affinity to an interface, which affects both wetting and adsorption¹⁻³. In this work, the effect of molecular interactions in mixtures on wetting and adsorption was systematically studied using molecular simulations of sessile droplets.

Molecular dynamics simulations have been used numerous times in the literature for studying wetting and adsorption¹⁻²⁶. In many cases, pure components were studied, e.g. in Refs.^{5,6,10,12}. Also, mixtures were studied by some authors^{3,8,17,23}. Yet, mostly, mixtures of real substances were considered and specific systems were studied, such as argon+krypton²⁶, water+alcohols¹¹, brine + CO₂⁷, and brine + n-decane¹⁵. Alternatives are studies of model systems, by which the influence of different molecular interactions on macroscopic observables can be investigated in a systematic manner^{1-3,23,24,27}.

Model systems have been used for studying adsorption at solid-fluid interfaces^{23,28-33} and vapor-liquid interfaces³⁴⁻³⁷. Yet, in most cases, only two-phase contacts were considered. *Becker et al.*¹² studied the contact angle of the Lennard-Jones truncated and shifted (LJTS) fluid and elucidated the effect of the temperature, the solid density, and the solid-fluid interaction parameter on wetting. Furthermore, a correlation describing the influence of these parameters on the contact angle was also provided³⁸.

There are only a few studies in which the model mixture route has been used for elucidating the influence of the molecular interactions on both wetting and adsorption^{1-3,24}. *Schmid* and *Wilding*¹ studied the wetting of Lennard-Jones mixtures using Monte Carlo simulations as well as by a mean-field theory. The mixture employed in this study was symmetric, i.e. the components were identical and only the cross-interaction parameter was varied and the solid wall acted equally on both components. *Granados-Bazán et al.*²⁴ investigated binary Lennard-Jones mixtures, where the second component was a Lennard-Jones chain, and studied the effect of the chain length on the contact angle. *Jiang et al.*² studied binary Lennard-Jones mixtures and determined contact angles using the surface tensions. *Heier et*

*al.*³ studied droplets of symmetric Lennard-Jones mixtures and determined the contact angle and adsorption properties in both the liquid and the gaseous adsorption layer on the solid surface, while varying the strength of the solid-fluid interaction. In the aforementioned studies, the influence of the strength of the solid-fluid interaction on adsorption and wetting was studied. Yet, to the best of our knowledge, no studies are available on the influence of the unlike fluid-fluid interactions and competing effects between the fluid mixture interactions and the solid-fluid interactions in mixtures on wetting and adsorption.

In this work, sessile droplets of binary mixtures on planar walls were studied using molecular dynamics simulations of Lennard-Jones truncated and shifted (LJTS) model systems. Both the wetting (i.e. the contact angle) and the adsorption at the different two-phase contacts (including the structure of the adsorbate layers) as well as the three-phase contact were studied systematically. The fluid mixtures were the same as in Refs.^{35,39–41}, and, therefore, the bulk fluid properties, the vapor-liquid equilibrium as well as the vapor-liquid interfacial properties are well known.

This work is structured as follows: first, the molecular models and the simulation method are introduced. Then, the results for the different systems are presented and discussed: first, for the interfacial properties (structure and adsorption) of the two-phase contacts; second, for the three-phase contact and the contact angle. Finally, additional results on the influence of the solid-fluid interaction energy on wetting and adsorption are presented and discussed.

II. MODELING AND SIMULATION

A. Molecular model

In this work, the Lennard-Jones truncated and shifted (LJTS) potential was used for describing the interactions between all particles. The LJTS potential u_{LJTS} is defined as

$$u_{\text{LJTS}}(r) = \begin{cases} u_{\text{LJ}}(r) - u_{\text{LJ}}(r_c) & r \leq r_c, \\ 0 & r > r_c, \end{cases} \quad \text{with} \quad (1)$$

$$u_{\text{LJ}}(r) = 4\epsilon \left[\left(\frac{\sigma}{r}\right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma}{r}\right)^6 \right], \quad (2)$$

where u_{LJ} indicates the full Lennard-Jones potential; ε , σ , and r are the energy parameter, the size parameter, and the distance between two LJTS particles, respectively. Due to the truncation of the interatomic potential, no calculation of long-range corrections is necessary. The LJTS potential was used to describe all interaction types in the studied model systems, i.e. fluid-fluid, solid-solid, and solid-fluid. Six binary fluid LJTS mixtures were investigated that are labeled A to F. All six mixtures were studied at a single temperature, but in the entire composition range where vapor-liquid equilibria exist. In the following, the term 'mixture' refers to these six binary mixtures. The term 'system' refers to the entire simulation box comprising the solid wall and a fluid mixture.

In the binary mixtures, the high-boiling component is labeled as "1" and the low-boiling component as "2". The size and the mass of both components were the same in all cases, i.e. $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = \sigma$ and $M_1 = M_2 = M$. Furthermore, component 1 was the same in all six mixtures. All of the quantities reported in this work are given with respect to ε_1 , σ_1 , and M_1 ^{42,43}. Two different low-boiling components were employed: $\varepsilon_2/\varepsilon_1 = 0.9$ and $\varepsilon_2/\varepsilon_1 = 0.5$. Moreover, to describe the interactions between unlike LJTS particles in the fluid mixture, the modified Lorentz-Berthelot rules were used^{44,45}:

$$\sigma_{12} = \frac{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2}{2}, \tag{3}$$

$$\varepsilon_{12} = \xi_{12}\sqrt{\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2}, \tag{4}$$

where the single indices '1' and '2' indicate the interaction of two particles of the same component and the double index '12' indicates the cross-interaction between different components. Three values for ξ_{12} were chosen: 1, 1.2, and 0.85. The six binary mixtures were obtained by varying $\varepsilon_2/\varepsilon_1$ and ξ_{12} .

In previous works of our group, these six mixtures were investigated regarding their vapor-liquid equilibrium and interfacial properties^{35,40,46} as well as bulk phase transport and excess properties^{41,47}. The six mixtures exhibit a wide variety of boiling behavior (cf. Fig. 1): from closely ideal, in the sense of Raoult's law (mixture A), to high-boiling and low-boiling azeotropic (mixtures B and C), mixtures with a supercritical component (mixtures D, E, and F), and mixtures with liquid-liquid miscibility gap (mixtures C and F). At the temperature studied here, only mixture F exhibits a liquid-liquid miscibility gap; mixture C forms a low-boiling azeotrope. The mixtures A to C are referred to as subcritical mixtures

($\varepsilon_2/\varepsilon_1 = 0.9$), whereas the mixtures D to F as supercritical mixtures ($\varepsilon_2/\varepsilon_1 = 0.5$) in the following.

The solid wall was represented by LJTS sites arranged on a face-centered cubic (fcc) lattice with the (100) surface exposed to the fluid. In all studied systems, the solid-solid interaction parameter was defined with respect to component 1's dispersion interaction energy as $\varepsilon_{ss} = 100 \varepsilon_1$. The size of the solid wall particles σ_s was the same as the fluid particles $\sigma_{ss} = \sigma$. A solid density of $\rho_s = 1.07 \sigma_{ss}^{-3}$ was chosen as in Ref.¹², which results in a lattice constant of $a = 1.55 \sigma_{ss}$. The surface of the solid is an atomistically ideal crystal without any lattice defects.

The solid-fluid interaction in the systems was related to the dispersive fluid-fluid interaction of a given fluid component by the solid-fluid interaction parameter ζ_i :

$$\varepsilon_{sf,i} = \zeta_i \varepsilon_i, \quad (5)$$

where i is component 1 or 2 and $\varepsilon_{sf,i}$ is the solid-fluid interaction energy of component i with the solid wall particles. The size parameter of the solid-fluid interaction was equal to the fluid particle size, i.e. $\sigma_{sf} = \sigma$.

This work consists of two parts: (i) studying different systems with different mixtures at constant ζ_i ; (ii) studying systems with a single mixture at different ζ_i . Table I gives an overview of the studied systems and the interaction parameters used therein. In (i), ζ_i is the same for both components, and its value is 0.5 (cf. Table I). These six systems are labeled A, B, C, D, E, and F in the following. In (ii), the solid-fluid interaction parameter ζ_i was

TABLE I. Overview of the systems studied in this work: parameters describing the fluid-fluid and the solid-fluid interactions (details given in the text) as well as the number of studied state points N_{points} .

System	Fluid mixture	ε_1	ε_2	ξ_{12}	ε_{12}	ζ_1	ζ_2	$\varepsilon_{sf,1}$	$\varepsilon_{sf,2}$	N_{points}
A	A	1	0.9	1	0.9486	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.45	9
B	B			1.2	1.1384					9
C	C			0.85	0.8064					9
C*						0.4	0.54	0.4	0.486	9
C**						0.55	0.405	0.55	0.3645	9
C***						0.6	0.36	0.6	0.324	9
D	D		0.5	1	0.7071	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.25	7
E	E			1.2	0.8485					9
F	F			0.85	0.6010					5

chosen differently for the two components (cf. Table I). These three systems are labeled as systems C*, C**, and C*** in the following. In all cases, also the pure component cases were studied.

For cases, where the solid-fluid interaction parameter is the same for both components ($\zeta_1 = \zeta_2 = \zeta$), the mean solid-fluid interaction energy can be estimated from the mole fraction of the components x_i and the solid-fluid interaction energy $\varepsilon_{sf,i}$ by

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_{sf} = x_1\varepsilon_{sf,1} + x_2\varepsilon_{sf,2} = x_1\zeta_1\varepsilon_1 + x_2\zeta_2\varepsilon_2 = x_1\zeta\varepsilon_1 + x_2\zeta\varepsilon_2 = \zeta(x_1\varepsilon_1 + x_2\varepsilon_2). \quad (6)$$

Eq. (6) can be applied to describe the interactions of both the vapor and the liquid phase with the solid phase. For systems A to C the mean solid-fluid interaction energy is the same for a given composition and the same holds for systems D to F. If the solid wall is considered as an external potential, the mean solid-fluid interaction energy $\bar{\varepsilon}_{sf}$ provides a measure for the attractive wall potential. With the help of the mean solid-fluid interaction energy $\bar{\varepsilon}_{sf}$, the competition between the fluid-fluid and the solid-fluid interactions can be discussed.

B. Simulation method

MD simulations of droplets sitting on a solid wall were carried out in the canonical ensemble with the program LAMMPS⁴⁸ to obtain results for the contact angle, the solid-vapor-liquid, the vapor-liquid, the solid-liquid, and the solid-vapor interfacial properties. The Nosé-Hoover thermostat was employed for controlling the temperature. The temperature was relaxed every 100 time steps and the time step was $\tau = 5 \times 10^{-4} \varepsilon_1^{-1/2} M_1^{1/2} \sigma$. All simulations were carried out at $T = 0.77 \varepsilon_1 k_B^{-1}$, which is approximately 70 % of component 1's critical temperature⁴⁹.

The substrate surface lies in the (x, y) -plane and has a quadratic area exposed to the fluid phase of $2,616 - 5,535 \sigma^2$. The origin of the simulation box was placed in one of the corners, cf. Fig. 2. At the beginning of the initialization, a half-sphere of the liquid phase ' (of radius $r = 18 - 23 \sigma$) was placed on the center of the solid surface. Then, the surrounding volume was filled with the corresponding vapor phase '' such that the total number of fluid particles was $N = 25,000$. *Becker et al.*¹² found that above $N = 10,000$, the contact angle does not depend significantly on the system size. The simulation box dimensions varied in different

simulations. With the choice of $N = 25,000$, it was ensured that the liquid phase consisted of at least 10,000 particles in all studied cases. In Ref.⁴⁹, it was shown that the curvature significantly affects the vapor-liquid surface tension γ_{VL} of the LJTS fluid when the droplets are relatively small ($r \lesssim 15 \sigma$). In this study, the droplet radius was at least $r = 18 \sigma$ such that the vapor-liquid surface tension is expected to be approximately the same as for the planar interface. The initial densities ρ' , ρ'' and compositions \underline{x}' , \underline{x}'' of the vapor and liquid phases were estimated using the PeTS equation of state³⁰.

Periodic boundary conditions were applied in all directions. Therefore, the droplet is effectively in a slit-like geometry. Hence, adsorption also occurs on the other side of the wall. To avoid the droplet interacting with the copy of the solid phase, the height of the simulation box (z -direction) was chosen significantly larger than the droplet radius. The box size was also large enough in x and y -direction so that the droplet (even for smaller contact angles) did not interact with itself across the periodic boundary conditions in these directions. The box edge length varied; its size was the same for the depth, width, and height for the simulation box with $L = 51 - 74 \sigma$. The number of solid particles varied according to the varying box dimensions, which was between 13,068 and 27,648. The thickness of the wall was 2.5 crystal unit cells (corresponding to approximately 4.5σ), which is larger than the cut-off radius. The simulation consisted of an equilibration for 3×10^6 time steps and production for 10^7 time steps. Fig. 3 exemplarily shows a snapshot of a droplet simulation.

The bulk phase properties and the density profiles were sampled in block averages with a length of 2×10^6 time steps, resulting in five sampling points in the production phase for each state point, for each property and profile. Bulk phase densities $\rho'_1, \rho'_2, \rho''_1, \rho''_2$ and pressure p', p'' were sampled in rectangular boxes in the corresponding phases (cf. regions V' and V'' in Fig. 2), which were positioned away from any interface such that they were unaffected by inhomogeneities. From the bulk densities ρ'_i and ρ''_i , the arithmetic mean density was calculated as $\rho_{50\%} = (\rho'_1 + \rho'_2 + \rho''_1 + \rho''_2)/2$.

For determining the density profiles, further sampling regions with different binning were defined, cf. Fig. 2. For determining the solid-fluid interfacial profiles, one-dimensional profiles of the local density were sampled. In the following, the 'center of the droplet' refers to the center of the base of the droplet, i.e. on the surface of the substrate. In this study, these one-dimensional density profiles are referred to using a tilde $\tilde{\rho}$. For obtaining the

density profiles of the solid-liquid interface $\tilde{\rho}'_1(z)$ and $\tilde{\rho}'_2(z)$, the component densities ρ'_1 and ρ'_2 were sampled in a rectangular volume V_{sl} placed within the droplet, cf. Fig. 2. In this volume, in the z -direction normal to the solid wall surface, the densities were sampled with a binning of $\Delta z = 0.0155\sigma$. In x and y -direction, the sampling box size was 12σ . The volume V_{sl} was placed in the center of the droplet. The starting point of the sampling in z -direction was at approximately 4.2σ and the endpoint was at approximately 14σ . These profiles were sampled in each block average.

The density profiles of the solid-vapor interface $\tilde{\rho}''_1(z)$ and $\tilde{\rho}''_2(z)$ were sampled similarly, with the volume V_{sv} placed in the vapor phase (cf. Fig. 2). The binning of the z -direction was again $\Delta z = 0.0155\sigma$. In x -direction, V_{sv} spans the entire box length. In y -direction, the width of V_{sv} was 6σ . The starting point of the sampling in the z -direction was at approximately 4.2σ ; the endpoint at approximately 12.5σ .

To evaluate the contact angle of the droplet, the local number densities of both components were additionally sampled on a 3D Cartesian grid in a volume V_{Θ} placed around the droplet (cf. Fig. 2). The volume V_{Θ} was chosen for each system individually such that the entire droplet was covered by V_{Θ} . The binning was equidistant in all dimensions ($\Delta x = \Delta y = \Delta z = 0.775\sigma$) resulting in a bin volume of approximately $0.5\sigma^3$. The number of grid points was on the order of 10^5 sampling points. In a post-production step, for each block average, using the density field obtained in the region V_{Θ} , the volume elements with densities of $\rho_{50\%} \pm 0.005\sigma^{-3}$ were identified. A sphere was fitted to the center point of the identified volume elements. The contact angle Θ was then evaluated using the coordinates of the center of the fitted sphere (x_c, y_c, z_c) , the fitted radius of the droplet, and geometrical/basic trigonometrical calculations. After determining the contact angle from the density field data $\rho(x, y, z)$ sampled in the region V_{Θ} , a coordinate transformation was applied to a polar coordinate system with the origin being placed on the center of the fitted sphere. From these polar coordinate system results, averaging over the angular coordinates θ and ϕ , the radial density profiles $\hat{\rho}_i(\hat{r})$ were determined, which also describe the vapor-liquid interface. Volume elements in the vicinity of the three-phase contact were excluded from the averaging. The distance \hat{r} was sampled in the range of $[0, 40\sigma]$.

Also, two-dimensional density profiles of the droplets were determined. The two independent variables are the z -dimension and the distance from the center of the droplet r in the x, y -plane. To obtain these two-dimensional profiles, a third way of sampling the

density was employed in the volume V_{3p} (cf. Fig. 2) with a resolution of 0.775σ in the x and y -direction and a 0.0155σ resolution in the z -direction. The number of grid points was approximately $3 - 4 \times 10^5$. The region V_{3p} was placed around the droplet (similar to V_Θ), with a thickness of 5.5σ in z -direction. From the density field data $\rho(x, y, z)$ sampled in region V_{3p} , a coordinate transformation was applied to a cylindrical coordinate system, with the origin being placed on the substrate surface in the center of the droplet. From these cylindrical coordinate system results and by averaging over the angular coordinate ϕ , the two-dimensional density profiles $\rho(z, r)$ were determined, which were used for describing the solid-liquid-vapor three-phase contact structure.

For characterizing the three two-phase contact interfaces, the surface excesses for components 1 and 2 were determined from the interfacial density profiles. The adsorption of component i at the solid-liquid and solid-vapor interface was computed as⁵⁰

$$\Gamma_i^* = \int_{z_0}^{z^*} \tilde{\rho}_i^*(z) - \rho_i^* dz, \quad (7)$$

where z_0 is the starting point, z^* is the endpoint of the integration (either z' or z''), and the star $*$ denotes either the liquid or the vapor properties (such as Γ_i' and Γ_i''). The point z_0 was chosen at the solid-fluid interface, such that $\tilde{\rho}_i^*(z)$, in both the liquid and the vapor phases, reaches the bulk density value, i.e. $\tilde{\rho}_i^*(z) - \rho_i^* \approx 0\sigma^{-3}$. The upper bound z' and z'' was chosen to ensure that $|\tilde{\rho}_i^*(z) - \rho_i^*| < 0.005\sigma^{-3}$ and the oscillation of the density profiles are decayed. These adsorption values give quantitative information about the number of excess particles accumulated at the solid-fluid interface. The interfacial thickness of the solid-liquid δ_i' and the solid-vapor interface δ_i'' was also calculated. The definition and the results are presented in the Supplementary Material.

Additionally, the vapor-liquid interface of the droplet was studied. The adsorption and the enrichment of the curved interface were computed using the radial density profiles $\hat{\rho}_i(r)$. The adsorption at the vapor-liquid interface $\Gamma_i^{(j)}$ was calculated as^{35,51}

$$\Gamma_i^{(j)} = -(\rho_i' - \rho_i'') \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\frac{\hat{\rho}_j(\hat{r}) - \rho_j'}{\rho_j' - \rho_j''} - \frac{\hat{\rho}_i(\hat{r}) - \rho_i'}{\rho_i' - \rho_i''} \right] dr \text{ with } i, j = 1, 2 \text{ and } i \neq j. \quad (8)$$

In this study, only results for $\Gamma_2^{(1)}$ are shown, as the complementary results $\Gamma_1^{(2)}$ do not provide

additional insights³⁵. The enrichment, which characterizes the monotonicity behavior of vapor-liquid interface density profiles^{35,39,52,53} was computed as

$$E_i = \frac{\max(\hat{\rho}_i(\hat{r}))}{\max(\rho'_i, \rho''_i)}. \quad (9)$$

The enrichment was computed only for the low-boiling component, i.e. E_2 . The relative adsorption and the enrichment are linked. Enrichment is usually only observed if the corresponding component also shows positive relative adsorption (i.e. $E_2 > 1$ when $\Gamma_2^{(1)} > 0$). In recent studies, it has been shown that strong enrichment is expected in binary mixtures if one of the components is supercritical as well as for low-boiling azeotropic mixtures^{35,39,54}. The vapor-liquid interfacial thickness was also evaluated. The results are presented in the Supplementary Material.

From each of the five block averaged density profiles ($\tilde{\rho}'_i(z)$, $\tilde{\rho}''_i(z)$, $\hat{\rho}_i(\hat{r})$, $\rho(z, r)$), the interfacial properties (Θ , Γ'_1 , Γ'_2 , Γ''_1 , Γ''_2 , $\Gamma_1^{(2)}$, and E_2) were calculated. Also, the bulk phase properties (ρ'_1 , ρ'_2 , ρ''_1 , ρ''_2 , p' , and p'') were determined as block average values in the respective volumes. The final value of the properties was determined as the mean value of the five block average values. The statistical uncertainties of the interfacial and bulk phase properties were estimated by the standard deviation of the five block average values.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First, the results for the adsorption and structure of the three two-phase interfaces (solid-liquid, solid-vapor, and vapor-liquid) are presented and discussed, followed by those for the three-phase interface (solid-liquid-vapor). In the main body of this work, the results for the systems A, B, C, D, E, and F are discussed in detail. For the systems C*, C**, and C***, only the results for the contact angle are presented here. The two-phase interfacial properties for systems C*, C**, and C*** are presented in the Supplementary Material. Where possible, results for the pure components are included. The numeric values of the simulation results are given in the electronic Supplementary Material.

A. Adsorption and structure at interfaces

1. *Solid-liquid interface*

Fig. 4 shows the solid-liquid interface density profiles normalized by the corresponding bulk densities for exemplary state points for the systems A, B, and C. The corresponding results for the systems D, E, and F are presented in the Supplementary Material. The state points depicted in Fig. 4 were chosen such that the liquid phase composition was approximately the same for the three systems A, B, and C, and two liquid phase compositions are considered: one, which is rich in component 1 ($x'_2 \approx 0.3 \text{ mol mol}^{-1}$) and the other is rich in component 2 ($x'_2 \approx 0.7 \text{ mol mol}^{-1}$). The overall structure of the solid-liquid interface is similar for the different systems, exhibiting strong oscillatory layering – as expected. Yet, some differences are observed regarding the competitive adsorption behavior of the two components.

For component 1-rich liquid phase states, for the low-boiling component (cf. Fig. 4a), interestingly, system B exhibits the highest density peaks ($\xi_{12} = 1.2$), followed by system A's density peaks ($\xi_{12} = 1.0$), and the smallest density peaks are observed for system C ($\xi_{12} = 0.85$). The same trends are observed for the component 2-rich liquid phase composition for the high-boiling component's density profiles (cf. Fig. 4d). The strength of the dispersive interactions of the wall with the low-boiling component is the same in systems A, B, and C and the same holds true for the high-boiling component. Yet, the structure is slightly different, which is due to the varying binary interaction parameter ξ_{12} between

the two fluid components. The peaks of the density profiles of the two fluid components of system B are closer to each other than in the case of systems A and C. Stronger fluid-fluid mean dispersive interactions, i.e. higher ξ_{12} result in stronger oscillatory behavior in the solid-liquid interface. Hence, system B exhibits the largest density peaks and system C the smallest.

The trends are entirely different for the component 2 profiles at component 1-rich liquid phase compositions in these state points and for the component 1 profiles at component 2-rich liquid phase composition (cf. Fig. 4b and c). In these two cases, the density profiles of system C exhibit the strongest oscillatory layering, followed by the systems A and B. Weaker mean dispersive interactions in the fluid make the solid-fluid interactions more favorable and dominant, which increases the structure of the interface. With the increasing mean dispersive interactions (going from $\xi_{12} = 0.85$ to 1.0 and 1.2), the solid-fluid interaction becomes less dominant, which decreases the peak height of the density layer in the interface.

As expected, the density profiles of system A lie always between those of systems B and C, cf. Fig. 4. Yet, sometimes stronger (normalized) absorption is observed for system B (components like each other), sometimes for system C (components do not like each other). What happens exactly, depends on the component we are considering as well as on its bulk concentration. As both components have a similar tendency to adsorb, the adsorbate layer consists predominantly of component 1, if the bulk concentration of component 1 is high – and the same holds for component 2. The results show that, in the case of favorable unlike interactions, the component that is in excess is adsorbed preferably, while in the case of unfavorable interactions that component is adsorbed less. The unlike interactions are more important for diluted components than for components in excess. The results shown in Fig. 4 indicate that the main influence comes from the interactions in the bulk: for favorable unlike interactions in the bulk (mixture B), less of the diluted component absorbs (in panel 4c component 2, in panel 4b component 1).

Fig. 5 shows the results for the adsorption Γ'_i at the solid-liquid interface for both components 1 and 2. Results are shown for all studied state points and the systems A to C. The obtained trends differ significantly for the three subcritical systems A, B, and C – for both Γ'_1 and Γ'_2 (Fig. 5a and c). The adsorption of the pure low-boiling component is higher than the adsorption of the high-boiling component, which is as expected. In the case of system A, the adsorption of component 1 Γ'_1 decreases approximately linearly with

increasing mole fraction of component 2. Results for system B are more complex. For Γ'_1 (cf. Fig. 5a), a maximum is observed in the component 1-rich state points ($x'_2 < 0.5 \text{ mol mol}^{-1}$) and a minimum in the component 2-rich state points ($x'_2 > 0.5 \text{ mol mol}^{-1}$). The same complexity is observed for system C, however, opposite to system B results, a minimum is observed in the component 1-rich systems and a maximum in the component 2-rich systems. The trends of the results of Γ'_2 are practically mirrored compared to the results of component 1 – for all three shown systems A, B, and C.

The results on the left side of Fig. 5 are closely related to those shown in Fig. 4; the concentrations considered in Fig. 4 are indicated in Fig. 5. The interpretation given in the discussion of Fig. 4 is confirmed by the results shown in Fig. 5 (left side). For low concentrations x'_i , favorable unlike bulk interactions (system B) lead to lower relative adsorption Γ'_i than unfavorable unlike bulk interactions (system C). However, this argument is based on the assumption that the like interactions are not too different for both components (comparing 1-1 and 2-2 interactions). The influence of the variation of the like interactions can be seen by comparing the left and the right column in Fig. 5. The mixtures D to F (right) differ from the mixtures A to C by the lower dispersion energy of component 2 (which results in the fact that component 2 is supercritical at the studied temperature so that mixtures D to F have a critical point, cf. Fig. 1). Mixtures B and E (blue) have stronger cross-interactions compared to weak cross-interactions in mixtures C and F (red) and the ideal mixtures A and D in between. A notable difference between the cross-interactions in mixtures A to C and mixtures D to F is that, in the latter group, the strength of the cross-interactions is always between those of the pure components, while this is not the case for the former group (see Table I).

In the case of system A, the number of component 1 particles decreases in both the liquid and the vapor phase with increasing x'_2 . Hence, the adsorption Γ'_1 decreases with increasing x'_2 (cf. Fig. 4a and b). Adsorption results Γ'_1 for system B are larger than for system A for component 1-rich liquid phase compositions, which is due to the larger density (more available particles). However, with further increasing mole fraction x'_2 , the adsorption Γ'_1 decreases and even becomes negative for system B. This is due to the stronger mean dispersive interactions in the fluid in mixture B compared to mixture A and the dominance of component 1-component 2 interactions over the solid-fluid interactions in that case. In the case of system C, Γ'_1 decreases first with increasing x'_2 . With further increasing

x'_2 , the component 1-component 2 interactions become dominant (which is energetically less favorable for system C compared to systems A and B), resulting in more favorable solid-fluid interactions. Hence, more particles adsorb on the surface. The same reasoning can be used for understanding the trends of the adsorption of component 2 Γ'_2 , cf. Fig. 5c.

The right column of Fig. 5 shows results for the adsorption Γ'_1 and Γ'_2 for the systems D, E, and F. The results for these three systems show the same picture: the adsorption of component 1 decreases with increasing liquid phase mole fraction x'_2 . The difference is only quantitative. With increasing mole fraction x'_2 , the component 1 particles desorb, whereas component 2 particles adsorb. The slope of the adsorption isotherms $\Gamma_2(x'_2)$ depends on the binary interaction parameter ξ_{12} and, therefore, on the mean dispersive interactions between the fluid particles. Yet, the variation of ξ_{12} does not result in such qualitative differences for the supercritical systems compared to the subcritical systems. This is in line with the previous studies of the same six fluid mixtures, where properties, such as interfacial properties³⁵ and the transport properties⁴¹ were studied. In these studies, no significant qualitative effect of the binary interaction parameter on the properties of supercritical mixtures was observed.

2. *Solid-vapor interface*

Fig. 6 shows the solid-vapor interface density profiles normalized by the corresponding bulk densities for the same liquid phase compositions (hence, differing vapor phase compositions) as shown in Fig. 4. The corresponding results for the systems D to F are presented in the Supplementary Material. The structure of the solid-vapor interface is similar for the different systems, exhibiting one distinct adsorption layer directly at the surface. For both, the component 1-rich and the component 2-rich states (left and right column of Fig. 6), the first density peak is approximately at the same height for each component. This is not surprising, as the solid-fluid interaction parameters $\varepsilon_{sf,1}$ and $\varepsilon_{sf,2}$ are the same for the three systems. The influence of the unlike fluid mixture interactions on the adsorbate layer is less pronounced for the vapor phase adsorption than for the liquid phase adsorption. Nevertheless, an influence can be discerned, but mainly regarding the (faint) second adsorbate layer. The formation of that second layer is favored by unfavorable cross-interactions, in all studied cases. System B has the strongest mean dispersive fluid interactions ($\xi_{12} = 1.2$) that dominate over the solid-fluid interaction and suppress the formation of a second adsorption

layer.

Fig. 7 shows the results for the adsorption at the solid-vapor interface Γ_i'' of both components for the six systems A to F. Adsorption data obtained from the solid-vapor interface have smaller uncertainties than those from the solid-liquid interface. However, the uncertainty of the sampled vapor phase mole fraction x_i'' is larger than the uncertainty of the liquid phase mole fraction x_i' (compare Fig. 5 to 7), which is due to the smaller number of particles in the case of the vapor phase. The adsorption results shown in Fig. 7 for both components follow in all cases a non-linear behavior as a function of mole fraction x_2'' . Yet, no minimum-maximum structures of adsorption isotherms are observed for Γ_i'' – opposite to Γ_i' .

In panels a, c, and d of Fig. 7, classical adsorption isotherms are depicted: the surface excess of component i increases with increasing bulk phase concentration of component i . Note that $x_i = 0.0 \text{ mol mol}^{-1}$ is on the left in panels 7c and d, whereas it is on the right in panel a. The results from panel b differ, as the origin of the adsorption isotherm $\Gamma_1(x_1)$ at $x_1 = 0.0 \text{ mol mol}^{-1}$ is not reached as component 2 is supercritical. In all panels, adsorption isotherms for the different values of the unlike interactions are shown. Also, pure component results ($x_i = 1.0 \text{ mol mol}^{-1}$) are shown. The three isotherms converge to these pure component values – as expected. This is the case for all results shown in Fig. 7. The adsorption isotherms from panels a and c are as expected: favorable unlike interactions in the bulk (mixture B) lead to weaker adsorption than unfavorable unlike interactions in the bulk that favor adsorption (mixture C). In contrast, the different values for the unlike interactions only have a minor influence on the adsorption isotherms of the mixtures D to F. This is related to the fact that in mixtures D and E, the strength of the cross-interactions ε_{12} is always between those of the pure components (ε_1 and ε_2), cf. Table I. Hence, the variation of ξ_{12} is not as dominant as for the mixtures A to C.

The qualitative behavior of the adsorption isotherms Γ_i'' (cf. Fig. 6) is very similar to the shape of the phase envelopes (cf. Fig. 1). The adsorption Γ_i'' obtained for the system B is lower than that obtained for system A (cf. Fig. 6a and c) – in the entire composition range. On the other hand, for some compositions, i.e. close to the azeotropic composition, the adsorption results for system C are larger than those for the systems A and B (holds for both components). For other composition values (mainly in the vicinity of the two pure component values), the vapor phase adsorption of component 1 for system C is similar to

system A, whereas for component 2, it is lower for system C, than for system A.

At concentrations larger than the azeotropic concentration of fluid mixture C, the vapor phase of system C contains the smallest concentration of component 2 particles (see Supplementary Material for exact values). Despite this, the adsorption values Γ_i'' for both components are larger than for other systems, which is due to the fact that the particles are more in favor of interacting with the solid particles. For example, this energetic preference is so significant that the density peaks for system C's component 2 are larger than system B's peak – despite the smaller concentration.

The vapor phase adsorption results from the supercritical systems (cf. right column of Fig. 7) are qualitatively and quantitatively similar for the systems D, E, and F. However, this is not surprising, as – compared to the results of systems A to C – changing the binary interaction parameter ξ_{12} does not cause a significant alteration in the mean dispersive interactions in the fluid. This is in line with the solid-liquid adsorption results and the findings for other thermophysical properties^{35,41}. Only some minor differences between the results for the systems D to F are observed, e.g. in the component 1 adsorption results Γ_1'' (cf. Fig. 7b), where the slope of the adsorption isotherms differ slightly. For the component 2 adsorption Γ_2'' (cf. Fig. 7d), the results from the supercritical systems D to F even agree within the statistical uncertainties in almost all cases. Hence, the competition effects of the solid-fluid and the fluid-fluid interaction practically vanish for the adsorption behavior of the supercritical component at the solid-vapor interface.

3. Vapor-liquid interface

The planar vapor-liquid interfacial properties of the six fluid mixtures A to F have been extensively studied in Refs.^{35,46}. Hence, the vapor-liquid interfacial properties (of the curved interface) are only briefly discussed here, focusing on the relevant aspects influencing the wetting and adsorption behavior. The fact that the vapor-liquid interface of the droplet, as it is studied here, is curved, in contrast to the previous studies, in which planar interfaces were studied, plays no significant role as the droplets were large enough to prevent any noticeable influence of the curvature. A comparison of the results from the curved interface and planar interface results from the literature is given in the Supplementary Material.

Fig. 8 shows examples for vapor-liquid density profiles for the systems A and C obtained

in this work. For the vapor-liquid interface, no layering structure is observed – in contrast to the solid-fluid interfaces. Yet, it should be noted that oscillatory layering may also occur at fluid interfaces at states below the Fisher-Widom temperature⁵⁵. For the pure LJTS fluid, this temperature was estimated to be at about $T/T_c = 0.9$ ^{56,57}. The fact that no significant vapor-liquid interface layering was observed here despite the fact that the temperature considered in this work is below the Fisher-Widom temperature is probably due to significant surface fluctuations that obscure the layering. Fig. 8 also shows that in some cases an enrichment of the low-boiling component was observed at the interface. The enrichment (quantifying the relative peak height of the profiles) is an interesting property, as it is suspected to influence the mass transfer across interfaces^{58,59}, which is also likely relevant for evaporating droplets on walls.

Fig. 9 shows the results for the enrichment of component 2 E_2 and the relative adsorption $\Gamma_2^{(1)}$ determined from the vapor-liquid density profiles. The enrichment and relative adsorption results obtained in this work for the curved interface of sessile droplets are qualitatively in good agreement with the results for the planar interface, see Supplementary Material. Significant enrichment is observed for the systems C, D, and F. The enrichment E_2 is always the highest for infinite dilution and decreases with increasing mole fraction x'_2 . It should be noted that the enrichment is a result of the thermodynamic behavior of a given mixture⁴⁰, which is opposite to the oscillatory layering, which is primarily a structural property. The results for the adsorption at the vapor-liquid interface are qualitatively similar to those for the solid-liquid interface adsorption (cf. Fig. 9), especially for component 2. This is not entirely surprising, as both properties refer to the same liquid phase, albeit in contact with different second phases.

4. *Three-phase contact*

Fig. 10 shows the results for the density of both components in the region of the three-phase contact. The density is indicated by the color as a function of two spatial coordinates (cf. Fig. 2, bottom): r the distance from the symmetry axis of the droplet and z the Euclidian distance from the wall surface. The width of the window is 35σ in the r -direction and about 4σ in the z -direction. The curvature of the vapor-liquid interface is negligible in the small window that is shown in Fig. 10. The contact angle is about 90° in both cases

that are represented in the two columns of Fig. 10 (mixtures A and D with liquid phase mole fractions of component 2 of about $x'_2 = 0.09 \text{ mol mol}^{-1}$). In the upper row, the results for the density of component 1 are shown; in the lower row, those for component 2. The four plots are qualitatively similar. A strong layering is observed on the liquid side (left part of the plot), while on the vapor side, only a single weak absorption layer is visible – with the exception of the plot for the density of component 2 in system D (lower right panel) for which the vapor and the liquid densities differ not so much and a faint second adsorption layer can be discerned on the vapor phase side. The layers on the vapor side can be considered as extensions of the layers on the liquid side (where the layering is stronger). The three-phase contact is basically the region in which the density in the first layer changes from its value on the liquid side to that on the vapor side, which is about 2σ wide for the depicted cases. The corresponding results for other cases are presented in the Supplementary Material.

Interesting observations are made for the systems with strong enrichment of component 2 at the vapor-liquid interface (compare lower right panel in Fig. 10 that shows results for system D with enrichment to the lower left panel in Fig. 10 that shows corresponding results for system A without enrichment). The behavior of the systems' structure at the three-phase contact provides new insights regarding the interplay of the systems' two-phase properties. For system A (Fig. 10 left), no enrichment E_2 at the vapor-liquid interface occurs. For system D (Fig. 10 right), a significant enrichment E_2 is observed. Upon approaching the three-phase contact along the vapor-liquid interface, interesting effects are observed. In the case of system D, the enrichment interacts with the solid-fluid layering in the three-phase contact region. For the second and third solid-liquid adsorption layer peaks (see labels in the bottom-right panel of Fig. 10), the enrichment and the solid-fluid adsorption amplify each other. Closing on the surface, at the first adsorption layer peak and valley, the vapor-liquid interface enrichment is faded away. Hence, the structure of the solid-liquid interface layering dominates the vapor-liquid interface enrichment structure at the three-phase contact. This can be well understood from the fact that the solid wall acts as a significantly stronger external potential compared to the external field effect of the vapor phase on the liquid phase.

B. Contact angle

1. Systems A, B, C, D, E, and F

Fig. 11 shows the results for the contact angle $\cos(\Theta)$ of the droplets on the wall. Results are shown for the systems A to C (left) and the systems D to F (right). A plot of the $\Theta(x'_2)$ results is given in the Supplementary Material. The attractive interactions exerted by the solid wall on component 2 $\varepsilon_{sf,2}$ are slightly weaker than on component 1. Therefore, it is expected that the contact angle of the pure component 2 should be larger than for the pure component 1 droplet. However, these differences cannot be discerned in the simulation results, which yielded contact angles that agree within the statistical uncertainty for both pure components. Results from this work for droplets with a pure component were compared with those reported by *Becker et al.*¹². The two datasets agree within the error bars, see Supplementary Material for details.

The results obtained for the contact angle in the different systems always converge to the pure component values – except in the cases where component 2 is supercritical. In the case of the practically ideal mixture A, the contact angle depends hardly on the composition, which can be understood as a consequence of the fact that the different interactions in the fluid are similar and also the attractive forces of the wall on the two components are similar. The only difference when going from system A to the systems B and C is that the unlike attraction in the fluid mixture is increased for mixture B, while it is decreased for mixture C. Increasing the strength of the unlike interactions (mixture B) leads to a decrease of $\cos(\Theta)$, i.e. an increase in Θ , corresponding to a deterioration of the wettability, as expected. The inverse is true for the decrease of the strength of the cross-interactions (mixture C). The shape of the curves in the left panel of Fig. 11 is a consequence of the fact that the cross-interactions are more important at intermediate mixing ratios of both components.

This explanation does not hold for the right panel of Fig. 11, where the results for the systems D to F are shown. Here, there is a strong difference in the attractive fluid-wall interaction between both components (it is significantly lower for component 2 than for component 1) and the numbers for the cross-interaction in the fluid are always between the values of the pure components (which is not the case for systems A to C, see Table I). Hence,

increasing the mole fraction of component 2 yields decreased solid-fluid interactions for all studied mixtures, which, in turn, leads to a lowering of the wettability and a decrease of $\cos(\Theta)$, i.e. an increase in Θ .

The qualitative behavior of the contact angle results for the three systems A, B, and C are similar to the qualitative behavior of other macroscopic properties of these systems, e.g. the vapor-liquid interfacial properties³⁵ and the transport properties⁴¹. System A – with a practically ideal mixture in the sense of Raoult’s law³⁵ – exhibits a linear dependency of the contact angle as a function of the mole fraction x'_2 . Furthermore, for all composition values, the contact angles are approximately the same as the pure component values. The reason for this is the same, as for the two pure component values: the competition of the fluid-fluid cross-interaction (ε_{12}) and the solid-fluid interactions ($\bar{\varepsilon}_{\text{sf}}$) is approximately the same with increasing mole fraction x'_2 .

For system B, the contact angle $\cos(\Theta)(x'_2)$ exhibits a minimum. Mixture B has $\xi_{12} = 1.2$, which results in an increased cross-dispersive interaction (1-2 interactions stronger than 1-1 and 2-2), and forms a high-boiling azeotrope, cf. Fig. 1. It also has a maximum in the surface tension approximately at the azeotropic composition^{35,60}, see Supplementary Material for more details. Usually, an extremum in the vapor-liquid surface tension is called an aneutropic point^{51,61}. For mixture B, the composition of the aneutropic point and the azeotropic point are approximately the same, and, in particular, agree also reasonably well with the composition of the minimum of the $\cos(\Theta)$. The same holds for the low-boiling azeotropic mixture C.

The contact angle behavior of system B can be understood from the vapor-liquid surface tension and the Young equation, which can be written as

$$\cos(\Theta) = \frac{\gamma_{\text{sv}} - \gamma_{\text{sl}}}{\gamma_{\text{vl}}}, \tag{10}$$

where γ_{sv} is the solid-vapor surface tension, γ_{sl} is the solid-liquid surface tension, and γ_{vl} is the vapor-liquid surface tension. The solid-fluid surface tensions γ_{sv} and γ_{sl} are mostly determined from the solid-fluid interaction energy⁶², which is constant for systems A to F. Hence, the solid-fluid surface tensions change less than the vapor-liquid surface tension γ_{vl} with varying composition. Hence, the composition dependency of the contact angle is dominated by the composition dependency of the vapor-liquid surface tension. If the vapor-

liquid surface tension has a maximum (which is the case for mixture B), it results in a minimum in the $\cos(\Theta)(x'_2)$, and, hence, a maximum in $\Theta(x'_2)$.

In more detail, as the contact angle arises from the interplay of the three interfaces, the strengthened fluid-fluid interactions make the solid-fluid interaction energetically less favorable, the fluid particles 'like' each other more than they 'like' the solid particles. Therefore, the contact angle of system B is larger compared to system A. This can be seen throughout the whole composition range (beware that the increase in Θ means that $\cos(\Theta)$ is decreased).

When ξ_{12} is decreased to 0.85 for system C, the qualitative and quantitative changes are the same as for system B, but in opposite direction (1-2 interactions are weaker than 1-1 and 2-2). With the decreased fluid-fluid interaction energy, it is more favorable for the particles to interact with the solid, although ε_{12} is still higher than $\varepsilon_{\text{sf},1}$ and $\varepsilon_{\text{sf},2}$. Therefore, no perfect wetting is observed. Seemingly, the minimum contact angle (or maximum in the $\cos(\Theta)$) is reached in the vicinity of the azeotropic point.

The contact angle has qualitatively the same behavior for the three systems D, E, and F: it monotonously increases with increasing mole fraction x'_2 . This is in accordance with several other interfacial (and fluid transport) properties^{35,41}, i.e. the cross-interaction parameter ξ_{12} has only a minor impact for systems with a supercritical component compared to systems, where both fluid components are subcritical. For the systems D, E, and F, in the fluid, the 1-2 interactions are weaker than the 1-1, but stronger than the 2-2 interactions. Also, there is a significant difference between the two solid-fluid dispersion energies $\varepsilon_{\text{sf},2} \ll \varepsilon_{\text{sf},1}$. The picture is similar to system A, but due to the more significant differences between the two components, the competition between the fluid-fluid and the solid-fluid interactions do not balance each other and the contact angle increases (i.e. $\cos(\Theta)$ decreases) with increasing mole fraction x'_2 . This behavior is most prominent for system E, where stable droplets with large concentrations of component 2 were obtained, which yield particularly high contact angle values.

2. *Systems C*, C**, and C****

The effect of the solid-fluid interaction parameter ζ_i for the two components, while keeping all other parameters constant, was also investigated, see Table I. This can be understood as a variation of the type of surface, while the fluid mixture is the same. The solid-fluid

interaction energy of component 1 increases in the series: $C^* \rightarrow C \rightarrow C^{**} \rightarrow C^{***}$, while in the same series, the solid-fluid interaction energy of component 2 decreases (see Table I). The solid-liquid and solid-vapor interfacial properties are reported in the Supplementary Material.

Fig. 12 shows the results for the contact angle $\cos(\Theta)(x'_2)$ for all four 'C' systems, i.e. C^* , C , C^{**} , and C^{***} . As for the results for the systems A to F, plots for $\Theta(x'_2)$ for the 'C' systems are given in the Supplementary Material. For pure component 1 (left side in Fig. 12), the solid-fluid interaction energy increases going from C^* to C^{***} and, as a consequence, the contact angle Θ decreases, i.e. $\cos(\Theta)$ increases. The inverse should be true for pure component 2 (right side in Fig. 12), where, however, three of the points lie so close that the differences are below their uncertainties. As discussed for the results for system C in Fig. 11, the maximum in the curves of the results for the four C-systems shown in Fig. 12 is a consequence of the unfavorable cross-interactions in the C mixture, leading to a decrease of the contact angle Θ (an increase in $\cos(\Theta)$). This effect is superimposed with the effect of the differing strength of the solid-fluid interactions for the two components. Increasing $\varepsilon_{sf,1}/\varepsilon_{sf,2}$ shifts the maximum to higher values of x'_1 (lower values of x'_2) – as expected.

Interestingly, the four data sets shown in Fig. 12 intersect in a common point within the statistical uncertainties of the results at about $x'_2 = 0.7 \text{ mol mol}^{-1}$. This composition is close to that of the azeotropic point of the fluid mixture, which is at $x'_2 = 0.669 \text{ mol mol}^{-1}$ according to the PeTS EOS and the same for all four C-systems considered in Fig. 12, as they only differ in the solid-fluid interactions. This leads to the hypothesis, that for azeotropic mixtures, the contact angle on walls with different preferences for the individual components are similar. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that this hypothesis has been stated. The hypothesis can also be discussed using the Young equation (Eq. 10), in which the denominator γ_{vl} is the same for all C-systems. From the fact that we find that $\cos(\Theta)$ is similar for walls with different preferences for the components, we conclude that also the difference $\gamma_{sv} - \gamma_{sl}$ should be independent of the preferences of the solid wall for the different components. This makes sense, as at the azeotropic point, the composition of the vapor and the liquid phase are the same.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, the adsorption and wetting behavior of different binary Lennard-Jones mixtures was studied using molecular dynamics simulation of sessile droplets on planar walls. The fluid mixture interactions, and in particular the cross-interactions, have a significant influence on the interfacial properties. While this is expected and well-understood for vapor-liquid interfaces, some findings obtained for solid-fluid interfaces are surprising. Furthermore, also walls with different preferences for the two components (different ratios of the corresponding solid-fluid interactions of the two components) were studied.

The competing effects of the fluid-fluid interactions and the solid-fluid interactions on different macroscopic properties were elucidated: the structure and adsorption behavior of all three participating interfaces (vapor-liquid, solid-liquid, and solid-vapor) were systematically investigated and put in relation to the three-phase contact and wetting behavior. The fluid-fluid interactions in the mixtures play a significant role, not only on the vapor-liquid interface, but also on the solid-liquid, solid-vapor, and the solid-liquid-vapor interfacial structure, adsorption, and the contact angle.

It would be interesting to extend the present study to other types of interactions (e.g. polar interactions), even though we speculate that the basic findings regarding the competition of unlike and like interactions in the fluid and the solid-fluid interactions do not depend on the type of attractive interactions that is studied.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

In the Supplementary Material, results for the solid-liquid and solid-vapor interfacial density profiles for systems D, E, and F are presented. The solid-liquid, solid-vapor, and vapor-liquid interfacial thickness results are also presented for systems A to F. For the solid-vapor interface, the composition of the vapor phase adsorbate layer is presented. Moreover, two-dimensional density profiles for various compositions for system D are presented. Furthermore, the vapor-liquid interfacial properties of the sessile droplets (the relative adsorption $\Gamma_2^{(1)}$ and enrichment E_2) are compared to the planar interface results of *Stephan et al.*³⁵ for systems A to F. The solid-liquid and solid-vapor adsorption properties, and the vapor-liquid interfacial properties for systems C to C*** are also presented. Pure component 1

contact angles are compared to results of *Becker et al.*¹² Moreover, all MD simulation results are reported in an electronic spreadsheet.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge funding of the present work by Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft DFG within CRC 926 and the EU Horizon project BATCAT. The simulations were carried out on the ELWE supercomputer at Regional University Computing Center Kaiserslautern under the grant TUKL-MTD. The present research was conducted under the auspices of the Boltzmann-Zuse Society of Computational Molecular Engineering.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interest to declare.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

All data obtained from the MD simulations are provided in the electronic Supplementary Material in a spreadsheet file. An explanation of that data is given in the Supplementary Material PDF file that can be found here [link].

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FIG. 1. Isothermal $p - x$ phase diagrams for the six mixtures A to F at $T = 0.77 \epsilon_1 k_B^{-1}$. The symbols are MD simulation results, the lines represent PeTS EOS results.

FIG. 2. Schematics of the simulation box (not true to scale): top view (top) and side view (bottom). The volumes V' and V'' consist of a single sampling bin (for determining the bulk phase properties). The volumes V_{sl} and V_{sv} consist of one-dimensional bins in z -direction. The volumes V_{Θ} and V_{3p} consist of bins discretizing all Cartesian coordinates x , y , and z . The coordinates of the center of the fitted sphere are x_c , y_c , and z_c , which are used for evaluating the radial density profiles using a polar coordinate system.

FIG. 3. Simulation snapshot of the liquid droplet (L) surrounded by its vapor (V) on a solid wall (S). Results for system B at $x'_2 = 0.305(12)$ mol mol⁻¹ and $T = 0.77 \varepsilon_1 k_B^{-1}$. Blue and green spheres denote component 1 and 2 particles, respectively; gray spheres denote the solid wall particles. The figure also shows the contact angle Θ . The regions SL, SV, and VL enclosed by the dashed curves (not true to scale) schematically indicate, where the interfacial properties were evaluated. The notation 3P is used for the region, where the three phases (solid, liquid, and vapor) are in contact.

FIG. 4. Density profiles at the solid-liquid interface $\tilde{\rho}'_i / \rho'_i$ at $T = 0.77 \varepsilon_1 k_B^{-1}$ for systems A to C as a function of the z -coordinate for component 1 and 2 (top and bottom row, respectively). Results are for component 1-rich liquid state points with liquid compositions $x'_{2,A} = 0.291(16)$, $x'_{2,B} = 0.305(12)$, and $x'_{2,C} = 0.267(26)$ mol mol⁻¹ (left column) and for component 2-rich liquid state points with liquid compositions $x'_{2,A} = 0.688(20)$, $x'_{2,B} = 0.679(19)$, and $x'_{2,C} = 0.702(34)$ mol mol⁻¹ (right column). Black, red, and blue lines correspond to results for systems A, B, and C, respectively.

FIG. 5. Liquid phase adsorption Γ'_i isotherms at $T = 0.77\varepsilon_1 k_B^{-1}$ as a function of the liquid phase mole fraction of component 2 x'_2 . In the left column, results for systems A, B, and C are denoted with black, blue, and red squares, respectively. In the right column, results for systems D, E, and F are denoted with black, blue, and red squares, respectively. Symbols with gray color correspond to pure component results. Full symbols correspond to results for component 1; empty symbols for component 2. The arrows below the panel c indicate the state points for which density profiles are shown in Fig. 4.

FIG. 6. Density profiles for the solid-vapor interface $\tilde{\rho}_i'' / \rho_i''$ at $T = 0.77 \varepsilon_1 k_B^{-1}$ for systems A to C as a function of the z -coordinate for component 1 and 2 (top and bottom row, respectively). The results presented here are for the same component 1-rich liquid state points as in Fig. 4, with the vapor compositions $x_{2,A}'' = 0.418(40)$, $x_{2,B}'' = 0.246(42)$, and $x_{2,C}'' = 0.556(43)$ mol mol⁻¹ (left column) and for component 2-rich liquid state points with the vapor compositions $x_{2,A}'' = 0.779(63)$, $x_{2,B}'' = 0.892(61)$, and $x_{2,C}'' = 0.689(58)$ mol mol⁻¹ (right column). Black, red, and blue lines correspond to results for systems A, B, and C, respectively.

FIG. 7. Vapor phase adsorption Γ_i'' isotherms at $T = 0.77\epsilon_1 k_B^{-1}$ for systems A to C as a function of the vapor phase mole fraction of component 2 x_2'' . In the left column, results for systems A, B, and C are denoted with black, blue, and red squares, respectively. In the right column, results for systems D, E, and F are denoted with black, blue, and red squares, respectively. Symbols with gray color correspond to pure component results. Full symbols correspond to results for component 1, empty symbols for component 2. The arrows below the panel c indicate the state points, for which density profiles are shown in Fig. 6.

FIG. 8. Density profiles for the curved vapor-liquid interface as a function of the distance from the center of the fitted sphere at $T = 0.77\varepsilon_1 k_B^{-1}$. Black: component 1, red: component 2. The left panel shows results for mixture A at $x'_2 = 0.094(8)$ mol mol $^{-1}$ (solid lines) and $x'_2 = 0.896(18)$ mol mol $^{-1}$ (dashed lines). The right panel shows results for mixture C at $x'_2 = 0.111(6)$ mol mol $^{-1}$ (solid lines) and $x'_2 = 0.886(19)$ mol mol $^{-1}$ (dashed lines).

FIG. 9. Enrichment E_2 (top) and relative adsorption $\Gamma_2^{(1)}$ (bottom) at the vapor-liquid interface as a function of the liquid phase mole fraction x'_2 at $T = 0.77\varepsilon_1 k_B^{-1}$. The left column shows results for systems A, B, and C, denoted by black, blue, and red symbols, respectively. The right column shows results for systems D, E, and F, denoted by black, blue, and red symbols, respectively.

FIG. 10. Two-dimensional density profiles $\rho(z, r)$ for component 1 (top) and component 2 (bottom), for systems A (left) and D (right). Results for system A are at liquid phase mole fraction $x'_2 = 0.094(8)$ mol mol⁻¹, for system D at $x'_2 = 0.0843(89)$ mol mol⁻¹. The numbers within the bottom-right panel indicate the labeling of the density layers in the liquid phase (see discussion in the text).

FIG. 11. Results for the cosine of contact angle $\cos(\Theta)$ as a function of the liquid phase mole fraction x'_2 at $T = 0.77\varepsilon_1 k_B^{-1}$. Systems A, B, and C (left) are denoted by black, blue, and red symbols, respectively, systems D, E, and F (right) are denoted by black, blue, and red symbols. The gray symbols indicate pure component results.

FIG. 12. Results for the cosine of the contact angle $\cos(\Theta)$ as a function of the liquid phase mole fraction x_2' at $T = 0.77\varepsilon_1 k_B^{-1}$ for the systems C*, C, C**, and C*** (cf. Table I) and are denoted with purple, red, orange, and yellow squares, respectively.